

The Rate of non-Participation in Work in the Italian Regions

The non-participation rate in the Italian regions. Istat calculates the non-participation rate, which is constituted by a ratio that "[...] the numerator includes, in addition to the unemployed, also those who are not looking for work but would be available to work, and in the denominator together with the latter also the work (employed and unemployed). "

The non-participation rate in the Italian regions. Istat calculates the non-participation rate, which is constituted by a ratio that "[...] the numerator includes, in addition to the unemployed, also those who are not looking for work but would be available to work, and in the denominator together with the latter also the work (employed and unemployed). " The Istat data relate to 2019. In first place there is Sicily with a value of 40.00%, followed by Calabria with an amount equal to 38% equal to Campania. In the middle of the table there are Liguria with a value of the non-participation rate of 15%, followed by Umbria with a value of 14% on a par with the Marche. Lombardy closes the ranking with a value equal to 9.6%, Veneto with an amount equal to 9.1% and Trentino-Alto Adige with an amount equal to 6.6%.

North. The value of the rate of non-participation in work increased in Northern Italy in the period between 2009 and 2019. In 2009 the value of the rate of non-participation in work was equal to a value of 8.80% and subsequently increased up to a value of 9.60% or a variation of 0.80 units equal to a value of 9.09%. In the transition between 2010 and 2011 the value of the non-participation rate increased from an amount equal to 9.60 units up to a value equal to 9.70% or equal to a change of 0.10 units equal to an amount of 1.04%. In the transition between 2011 and 2012 the value of the non-participation rate in Northern Italy increased from an amount equal to 9.70% up to a value equal to 11.70% or equal to a value of 2.00 units equal to a value of 20.62%. In the transition between 2012 and 2013 the value of the non-participation rate went from an amount equal to 11.70% to a value equal to 13.10% or equal to a growth of 1.40 units equal to a value of 11.97%. In the passage between 2013 and 2014 the value of the non-participation rate in work increased from 13.10% up to a value of 13.70% or equal to a value of 0.60 units equal to a value of 4 , 58%. In the transition between 2014 and 2015 the value of the non-participation rate in Northern Italy decreased from an amount equal to 13.70 units to a value equal to 13.40 units or equal to a variation of -0.30 units equal to -2.19%. Between 2015 and 2016 the value of the non-participation rate in Northern Italy decreased from an amount equal to 13.40 units up to a value equal to 12.50 units or equal to a value of 0.90 units equal to a value of 6.72%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the non-participation rate decreased from an amount equal to 12.50% up to an amount equal to 11.60% or equal to a variation of -0.90 units equal to a value of 7.20%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of the non-participation rate decreased from an amount equal to 11.60 units up to a value equal to 10.90 units or equal to a value of -0.70 units equal to a value of -6.03%. In the passage between 2018 and 2019, the value of the non-participation rate in the macro-regions decreased from an amount equal to 10.90 units up to a value equal to 10.10 units or equal to a variation of -0 , 80 units equal to a value of -7.34%.

Central and Southern Italy. The trend in the non-participation rate in Central and Southern Italy had in the period between 2009 and 2019 a trend very similar to that of the North in terms of percentage changes, albeit with significant differences in terms of absolute values. Also for Central and Southern Italy the trend of the variable relating to the rate of non-participation in work grew until 2014 and

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subsequently between 2014 and 2019 had a decreasing trend. However, it must be considered that the value of the non-participation rate in Central Italy was on average equal to 4.39 units higher than the corresponding value in the North or an average value higher than 39.08%. In the case of Southern Italy, the value of the non-participation rate in the period between 2009 and 2019 was on average equal to approximately 23.36 points higher than the corresponding value in the North, i.e. an average value approximately double.

The variations in the rate of non-participation in work in the Italian regions between 2009 and 2019.

Furthermore, in the period between 2009 and 2019 the value of the rate of non-participation in work increased significantly for Campania which recorded a + 7.8%, followed by Sicily with + 7.7% and Calabria with a value of +7.2. In the middle of the table there are Piedmont with a value of 3.2%, Friuli-Venezia Giulia with a value of + 2.9%, and Molise with a value of + 2.8%. Lazio and Basilicata close the ranking with a value of +1.6 units followed by Veneto with an amount of +1.1 units. With reference to the macro-regions, it should be considered that in Southern Italy the rate of non-participation in work grew by 5.9% between 2009 and 2019, while in the North it grew by 2.5% and in the Center by 2.3. %.

Conclusion. The rate of non-participation in work tends to be closely related to the distribution of income. In regions where per capita income is higher, the rate of non-participation in work tends to decrease. This condition manifests the presence of regional labor markets with diverging efficiency. It is necessary to implement economic labor policies that are able to reduce the rate of non-participation in work through training courses also aimed at technological innovation and digitization. It should also be considered that especially in Southern Italy the emigration of the population, especially young people and of working age, is still very significant, which in the long run could lead to a further worsening of the North-South gap. Obviously, this inequality becomes serious above all in relation to the sustainability of the pension systems and budgets of the southern regions. In fact, if the question of fiscal federalism were to be raised in post-covid, and if this were to somehow be implemented, certainly Southern Italy could be indefinitely relegated to the scarcely productive areas of Europe. A pact is therefore needed between entrepreneurs, public officials, bankers and politicians for the relaunch of regional and interregional labor markets in Southern Italy.

Declarations

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